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AN ASSESSMENT OF THE EXTENT OF ADOPTION OF IMPROVED RICE PRODUCTION PRACTICES AMONG SMALL HOLDER FARMERS IN GULANI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF YOBE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The extent of adoption of improved rice production practices among smallholder farmers in Gulani Local Government Area of Yobe State, Nigeria, was examined. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to 240 smallholder farmers selected through a multistage sampling technique. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages. The results indicated high adoption rates for tractors in land preparation, planting of improved varieties, seed sorting, seed dressing materials, chemical fertilizers, and herbicides for weed control. In contrast, mechanical winnowers and threshers exhibited low adoption rates. It is recommended that policymakers promote the adoption of modern rice production practices by implementing extension delivery approaches such as Farmers' Field Schools and farm visits.

Keywords: Adoption, Rice Production, Farmers, Gulani

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa*), originally domesticated in India, is a major cereal crop with global significance. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2000), more than half of the world's population relies on rice for 80% of their dietary needs. Rice ranks as the second-most-produced cereal crop worldwide, following wheat, with approximately 512.4 million tons of milled rice produced annually (Childs and Lebeau, 2022). In Africa, rice is cultivated in lowland, rain-fed upland, and aquatic ecologies across most countries, covering nearly 10 million hectares (Zenna *et al*, 2017). Despite this extensive cultivation, outdated production systems, biotic and abiotic constraints, and limited investment in production technologies have resulted in only 60% of consumer demand being met through local production. In response, many African countries have implemented national strategic plans and favorable policies to increase production and achieve both local demand and export objectives.

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Rice is a principal staple crop in Nigeria, with cultivation dating back to 1500 BC and initially involving the indigenous, low-yield red grain variety *Oryza glaberrima* (Hopkins, 1973; Ogundele and Okoruwa, 2006). Presently, rice is grown across all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. The states with the highest production rates include Kebbi, Benue, Ebonyi, Ekiti, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Ogun, Niger, and Cross River. Demand for rice in Nigeria has increased more rapidly than in any other African country, driven by population growth, rising incomes, and urbanization, which have shifted consumer preferences. Current rice consumption in Nigeria is estimated at approximately 6.7 million metric tons (Enagi, 2022).

However, paddy production has not matched this demand due to continued reliance on traditional production methods, which are characterized by low yields and inefficiency. This production gap has resulted in lost employment opportunities for youth, increased currency outflow, and depletion of national foreign reserves. To address the disparity between demand and supply, as well as the needs of a growing population, the federal government of Nigeria has implemented policies and incentives to promote local rice production. In Yobe State, rice farming is primarily conducted by smallholder farmers who cultivate small plots using traditional methods, including local seeds, minimal fertilizer application, and inadequate post-harvest handling. Limited adoption of modern agricultural technologies has constrained productivity growth among these farmers. Consequently, encouraging the adoption of improved seeds and agricultural practices is essential to enhance crop yields and create employment opportunities. This study assesses the adoption and acceptability of improved rice production practices among smallholder farmers in Gulani Local Government Area.

Literature Review

Rice refers to the seed of the grass species *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice) or *Oryza glaberrima* (African rice). As a cereal grain, it is the most widely consumed staple food for a significant portion of the global population, particularly in Asia (FAOSTAT, 2017). The traditional cultivation method involves flooding fields during or after transplanting seedlings. This approach requires careful planning and maintenance of water management systems, but it suppresses the growth of less resilient weeds and pests that cannot survive submerged conditions and deters vermin. Although flooding is not essential for rice cultivation, alternative irrigation methods demand greater effort in weed and pest management and necessitate different soil fertilization strategies.

Empirical Literature

Challa (2014) notes that improvements in the input-output relationship resulting from new technologies tend to increase output and reduce average production costs, leading to substantial gains in farm income. Hailu, Abrha, and Weeldegiorgis (2014) examined the adoption and impact of agricultural technologies on farm income in Southern Tigray, Northern Ethiopia, using cross-sectional data collected through semi-structured questionnaires and analyzed with probit and ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. Their findings reveal a positive and significant effect on farm income, with adopters faring better than non-adopters. The study recommends that policymakers implement measures to address challenges faced by smallholder farmers in adopting modern technologies. Ibrahim (2014) investigated the adoption of rice production technologies among farming households participating in the Borno State Agricultural Development Programme, Nigeria. The study found that 62.2% of respondents adopted seed selection, 53.7% adopted improved seed varieties, 52.8% adopted land preparation techniques, and 56.4% and 56.0% adopted appropriate planting depth and plant spacing, respectively. Adeleye (2016) examines the adoption of improved rice production technologies among members and non-members of rice farmers' associations in Kaduna and Kano states. The study found that adoption rates exceeded 70% for 7 out of 13 improved rice production technologies.

Shaibu and Shaibu (2017) Adoption determinants of improved farming technologies: an assessment of rural rice farmers in Kogi state, Nigeria. The study found that 77.4% and 60.5% of the farmers adopted improved rice varieties and timely transplanting, respectively. Saliu *et al* (2016) examined the socio-economic determinants of the adoption of improved rice technologies by small-scale farmers in Kogi State, Nigeria. From the results, all farmers adopted agrochemicals (100%), and they were categorized into low, medium, and high adopters, with 60% being high adopters. Islam (2018) assesses the impact of adopting improved rice varieties on farmers' wellbeing in rural Bangladesh using primary household survey data. The analysis employed difference-in-difference with propensity score matching (DID-PSM). The findings demonstrate that improved rice technology has a robust and positive effect on farmers' welfare, as measured by increased household consumption expenditure and a reduced poverty gap.

MaMabe *et al.* (2018) analyzes the determinants of the adoption of improved rice varieties and their effects on rice output. The results indicate that 54% of respondents used improved rice varieties, while 46% did not. Onyekene (2017) investigated the determinants of adopting improved technologies in rice production in Imo State, Nigeria. The findings show that 73.33% of rice farmers adopted improved rice varieties, 67.41% used agrochemicals, 78.52% applied fertilizers, 86.67% used optimum seed rates, and 45.4% adopted mechanical harvesting.

Sheshi and Usman (2018) study the increase in rice production through the adoption of improved varieties in Niger State. Their findings reveal that 97.54% of respondents adopted the Faro 44 improved rice variety on their farms. Ogundari and Bolarinwa (2019) conduct a meta-regression analysis of 92 studies published between 2001 and 2015 in Sub-Saharan Africa. Their findings indicate that the adoption of agricultural innovations has a positive and significant effect on farm production and household welfare indicators. However, the magnitude of this impact is relatively small, suggesting a weak relationship.

Ahmed and Anang (2019) report that the adoption of improved agricultural technology serves as a means to increase agricultural production, raise farm income, reduce poverty, improve living standards, and enhance food security. Anissa (2013) investigated the impact of improved rice varieties on income and poverty reduction among rice farmers in Cameroon using primary household survey data and instrumental variable analysis. The results indicate a positive and significant impact of improved rice varieties on farm household income and poverty alleviation. Anissa recommends that adopting productivity-enhancing technologies can contribute to higher household incomes, poverty reduction, and improved food security in developing countries.

Obiora, (2023) in his study, "evaluation of value chain development programme on paddy rice production in Anambra State, Nigeria", reveal that the overall grand mean adoption of the farmers was 4.10 with adoption index of 0.82. The paddy rice farmers adopted the majority of the improved pre-planting technologies with a mean adoption score of 4.17. These include land selection ($\bar{X} = 4.52$), land preparation ($\bar{X} = 3.90$), seed selection from a certified agro dealer ($\bar{X} = 4.08$), seed germination rest ($\bar{X} = 4.65$) and treatment of seeds with insecticide ($\bar{X} = 3.71$). Their grand mean adoption score for planting depth and spacing, and bird scaring equipment were at the adoption stage of the adoption process with adoption mean score value of 5.00 while transplanting was at the trial stage $\bar{X} = 4.10$. whereas, nursery establishment, weed and pest control, timely planting, use of smart weather reader and water management were at the evaluation stages with mean adoption scores of 3.12, 3.00, 3.21, 3.95, 3.88, respectively. The grand mean score was 3.90 while the adoption index was 0.78.

Vihi, S.K., et al (2024) assess the adoption of improved production technologies among rice farmers in Wase Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used in the selection of 160 respondents for the study. Descriptive statistics, a four-point Likert scale and Logit regression were used to achieve the objectives of the study. Findings from the study revealed the farmers were 40 years old on average. A greater percentage (67%) of the farmers was men and 91% of them were married. The mean annual income of the farmers was estimated at N 202, 356. Improved rice production technologies, such as appropriate time of harvesting (3.44), land preparation by tractors (3.42), recommended time of weeding (3.41), appropriate planting dates (3.25), use of herbicides (3.24), improved seed varieties (3.11), application of recommended fertilizer (3.05), nursery practice and transplanting (2.73) all had high levels of awareness and adoption respectively among the farmers. Age, educational status, farming experience, farm size, extension contact and annual income were significant determinants of adoption of improved rice production technologies. High cost of technology (69%), inadequate extension contact (61%), and inadequate credit access (48%) and lack of accessibility of some technologies (28.0) were identified as the major constraints to the adoption of improved rice production technologies.

Obiora, C., C., et al (2024) study adoption of improved technologies among rice farmers. The study attempt to assess the adoption of improved technologies by rice farmers particularly the level of adoption of recommended technologies by rice farmers specifically examined the level of adoption of recommended technologies in rice production. The found that the farmers, adopt majorly improved technologies in the production of rice such as pre-planting, planting operations and the use of fertilizers but have low adoption of improved technologies in the processing of rice such as threshing, winnowing, and preservation of the rice products. The adoption of technologies by rice farmers is determined to be influenced by the farmers' social and economic power like level of education, financial status and general exposure/interaction with other farmers.

Aremu, P. A. Adewale, J. G. & Olaniyi, O. A. (2025) conduct a study on adoption of improved rice production technologies among rice farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria. Data were collected using a structured interview schedule. Descriptive statistics, frequency counts, percentages, means, and Weighted Mean Scores (WMS) were used to describe the study's objectives. In addition, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used to test the study's hypothesis. The findings revealed that the mean age of rice farmers was 45 years, while the grand mean number of years spent in formal school was 3 years. The mean year of experience in rice farming was 6.5 years, while the mean size of rice farm cultivated was 2.2 hectares. Extension teaching methods such as radio, contact farmers, small plot adoption techniques, method demonstration, and general meetings have been utilized to disseminate improved rice production technologies.

Aremu, P. A.; Adewale, J. G. and Olaniyi, O. A. (2026) carry out a study on utilization of improved rice production technologies among rice farmers in ekiti state, Nigeria. They employed multistage sampling procedure was to select 133 rice farmers for the study. Data was collected using a structured interview schedule. Descriptive statistics, frequency counts, percentages, means, and Weighted Mean Scores were utilized to describe the study's objectives. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was also used to test the study's hypothesis. The findings shown that the mean age of rice farmers was 44 years, while the mean household size was 4 people, and the grand mean number of years spent in formal schools was 4.1 years. The mean year of experience in rice farming was 5.2 years, while the mean size of rice farm cultivated was 2.9 ha, and the mean annual income was ₦595,420. Knapsack sprayer, rice farming inputs, and improved rice varieties were the types of improved rice production technologies utilized by the rice farmers on every occasion, while poor access roads and other infrastructure, lack of transport facilities, high cost of farm inputs, excessive weeds, and infestations of pests and diseases were the most strenuous and tough constraints encountered in rice farming. The study found a significant relationship between rice farmers age ($r=0.310$, $p=0.000$), household size ($r=0.409$, $p=0.000$), number of years of spent schooling ($r=0.131$, $p=0.034$), years of experience in rice farming ($r=0.505$, $p=0.000$), size of rice farm ($r=0.470$, $p=0.000$), and annual income ($r=0.142$, $p=0.000$) and utilization of improved rice production technologies among rice farmers.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Gulani LGA, in the southern part of Yobe state, Nigeria. The Local Government headquarters is located in Bara, at latitudes $10^{\circ}58'N$ and $53.07 N$, and longitudes $11^{\circ}39'E$ and $40^{\circ}65'E$. It covers an area of 2,090 km² and a projected population of 146,900 (National Population Commission, NPC, 2016). The study area has annual rainfall ranging from 500 mm to 1000 mm, which occurs from May to October (Nimet, 2018).

Primary data was used for this study. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires to obtain the required information from respondents. Field assistants were specifically trained for this research and used to administer the questionnaire. The questionnaire has been translated into Hausa for easy administration, since most farmers don't understand English, and it has been checked by a language expert. These sections would provide the information needed to realize the objectives of the study; the questionnaire was adapted from Tsinigo (2014) and modified to suit this study.

Multistage sampling, involving purposive and systematic sampling, was employed to select respondents for the study. The first stage involved purposive selection of the Gulani Local Government area of Yobe State, being one of the predominant areas of rice production. The second stage involved selecting five district wards from the twelve wards in the study area, as these wards have a high density of rice farmers. The third stage also involved systematic sampling procedure to select the respondents from the total population of 570 rice farmers in the five wards obtained from NECAS Yobe state office (2019), which served as the sampling frame, the sample size for this study was determined using a published table for selecting sample sizes by Israel (1992), who recommended that for a population of 600 a sample size of 240 is considered appropriate at $\pm 5\%$, precision level where confidence level is 95%. The sample size of 240 was distributed across the five wards using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula.

$$\frac{N \times S}{TP}$$

Where:

N = Number (population of each ward), S = Sample (total sample size) TP = Population of rice farmers

Results and Discussion.

The Extent of Adoption of Improved Rice Production Practices among Smallholder Farmers

Table 1 Extent of Adoption of Improved Rice Production Practices

	Adoption level			Practices								
	TLP	IV	SSP	SDM	HLC	HWC	NPK	UREA	MT	MW	RM	
Low	170	21	45	10	23	26	93	48	167	152	66	
Adoption	(71.1)	(8.9)	(19.0)	(4.2)	(9.7)	(11.0)	(39.2)	(20.3)	(70.5)	(64.1)	(27.8)	
Medium	54	107	139	106	100	72	94	71	46	45	53	
Adoption	(22.3)	(45.1)	(58.7)	(44.7)	(42.2)	(30.4)	(39.7)	(30.0)	(19.4)	(19.0)	(22.4)	
High	13	109	53	121	114	139	50	118	24	40	118	
Adoption	(5.5)	(46.0)	(22.3)	(51.1)	(48.1)	(58.6)	(21.1)	(49.8)	(10.1)	(16.9)	(49.8)	

Source: Field survey 2025

TLP: tractor for land preparation, **IV:** improved variety; **SSP:** sorting of seed planting seed; **SDM:** dressing material; **HLC:** herbicide for clearing; **HWC:** herbicide for weed clearing (pre-emergence); **NPK:** basal NPK application; **UREA:** top dressing with urea; **MT:** mechanical thresher; **MW:** mechanical winnower; **RM:** rice milling machine.

Use of Tractor for Land Preparation: Results presented in Table 1 indicate that 71.1% of respondents were categorized as low-level adopters of tractors for land preparation. Only 22.3% and 5.5% of adopters were found in the medium and high adoption levels, respectively. The low adoption rate may be attributed to limited availability of tractor hiring services, high costs, and lack of interest. These findings align with those of Ibrahim (2014), who reported that 52.8% of respondents adopted tractors for land preparation.

Use of Improved Variety: Analysis in Table 1 shows that 8.9% of respondents were in the low adoption category, 45.1% in the medium, and 46.0% in the high adoption category. The high adoption rate of improved varieties may be linked to government emphasis on rice production as a strategy to enhance agricultural productivity and revitalize the economy. This finding is consistent with Sheshi and Usman (2018), who reported that 97.54% of respondents adopted improved rice varieties on their farms. **4.3 Sorting of Seed for Planting:** Table 4.1 reveals that 22.3% of adopters were in the high adoption category, 19.0% in the low, and 58.7% in the medium adoption category. The medium adoption level may be attributed to traditional knowledge and skills related to seed storage for subsequent farming seasons. Additionally, training, frequent extension contact, and younger age may contribute to the medium adoption level of this technology in the study area. This is consistent with the findings of Ibrahim (2014), who reported that 62.2% of respondents adopted sorting of seed for planting.

Seed Dressing Material: Results in Table 4.1 show that 4.2% of adopters were in the low adoption category for seed treatment practices, while 44.7% and 51.1% were in the medium and high adoption categories, respectively. Low adoption levels may be due to institutional and psychological factors, such as lack of interest in recommendations, high costs, limited availability of inputs, and insufficient extension information. These findings are consistent with Donkor et al. (2018), who reported that only 31.28% of respondents in Northern Ghana adopted seed dressing materials. **Herbicide for Land Clearing:** The use of agro-chemicals remains an effective solution for controlling persistent weeds in rice fields. The efficacy of herbicides has been demonstrated at the farm level, and farmers are increasingly adopting modern weed control methods. Findings indicate that 42.2% of adopters used herbicides at the medium adoption level, 9.7% at the low level, and 48.1% at the high level. Limited availability of agro-chemicals, a constrained labor force, and high costs may contribute to these adoption patterns. This finding corroborates those of Adeleye (2016).

Herbicide for Weed Control after Planting (Pre-emergence): Herbicide adoption was relatively high, as it replaced hand weeding, which is labor-intensive and time-consuming. A total of 58.6% of adopters reported a high adoption level of this recommendation. These adopters considered herbicides an effective alternative to manual weeding, despite the associated costs and the technical knowledge required for application. The 11.0% low adoption rate may be attributed to high costs, limited availability of herbicides, and long distances to input markets, as reported by Ibrahim (2014).

Basal NPK Fertilizer Application: This refers to the recommended rate of inorganic fertilizer use. Study results indicate that 39.7% of respondents were medium-level adopters of basal fertilizer application, while 21.1% were high-level adopters and 39.2% were low-level adopters. Overall, adoption of the recommended fertilizer rate was generally at a medium level among farmers. This finding is consistent with Chekene and Chancellor (2015), likely because these inputs are complementary. The medium adoption level may be due to high fertilizer costs and limited availability at the required time and quantity.

Top dressing with Urea: The result showed that (49.8%). 4.8 Top Dressing with Urea: Results indicate that 49.8% of adopters were in the high adoption category, while 30.0% were in the medium category. Fertilizer application levels depended on availability and farmers' purchasing power. Low adoption (20.3%) occurred when limited quantities were available due to short supply or lack of funds. The low adoption rate may be attributed to high costs and insufficient supply of chemical fertilizer, resulting in application below recommended quantities and dosages, as reported by Donkor *et al.* (2018). That is (49.8%) it is believed that adopters in this category were already used to the traditional way of milling rice. So, this technology was seen as a compatible innovation even though it is capital-intensive. On the other hand, the technology recorded (22.4%) and (27.8%) of adopters in the medium and low adoption levels, respectively. **Mechanical Thresher:** Low adoption was observed, with 70.5% of respondents in the low adoption category. This suggests that most rice farmers in the study area did not adopt this practice. Medium and high adoption levels were 19.4% and 10.1%, respectively. Resource-constrained farmers lacked the means to procure motorized threshers, leading them to rely on manual, labor-intensive methods. Few respondents used mechanical threshers and winnowers, likely due to limited machine availability in the study area, as reported by Anang (2019).

Mechanical Winnowers: Findings indicate that 64.1% of adopters were in the low adoption category for this practice. Constraints included insufficient funds to purchase the machine and a lack of technical information and training. Only 16.9% of respondents were in the high adoption category. Low adoption may be attributed to limited information about the technology, unaffordable machine prices, and the absence of rental services.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that adoption rates for improved rice production technologies were high for tractor use in land preparation, planting of improved varieties, seed sorting, seed dressing materials, chemical fertilizer use, and herbicide for weed control. In contrast, adoption rates for mechanical winnowers and threshers were low.

The study also concluded that adopters of improved rice production practices faced several challenges that limited their ability to maximize farm outputs. These challenges included high input costs, inadequate tractor hiring services, and insufficient extension support, among others. Based on these findings, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- i. Policy makers should promote the adoption of modern rice production practices with currently low uptake. Hands-on extension delivery approaches, such as Farmers Field Schools and farm visits, should be introduced to enhance the adoption of these technologies.
- ii. The study also recommends that smallholder farmers form associations to facilitate mutual guarantees, enabling them to access existing credit facilities such as microfinance and agricultural banks. This would support expanded investment in rice production.

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